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IMPROVING THE CIRCULATING WATER COOLING DEVICE IN THE INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE

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Abstract: Currently, cooling systems with cooling tower are quite common (up to 70%). In them, water is used repeatedly, but part of the water is lost when it evaporates, and therefore it will be necessary to maintain the system regularly with clean water. Cooling tower circulating water partially evaporates and convection, that is, a decrease in temperature due to heat exchange with air. Further the economic feasibility of having additional cooling tower capacity to allow for economizer cooling, in light of reduced tower capacity at lower temperatures [3] is investigated. Creating rational water use schemes and reducing the consumption of fresh water taken from water supply systems or natural reservoirs can be a significant factor in improving the economic performance of the enterprise. The basis of rational water use schemes are water-circulation cooling systems, where cooling towers are used as cooling equipment.

Keywords: cooling tower, rational choice of type cooling tower, the renovation of the cooling tower; the maintenance of a cooling tower, cooling tower types.

Purpose. To consider the main criteria that should be guided with the choice of method for reconstruction of cooling towers to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of their operation.

INTRODUCTION. A cooling tower is a device that is used to cool a water stream while simultaneously rejecting heat to the atmosphere. In systems involving heat transfer, a condenser is a device that is used to condense the fluid flowing through it from a gaseous state to a liquid state by cooling the fluid. This cooling to the fluid flowing through a condenser, is generally provided by a cooling tower.

Cooling towers may also be used to cool fluids used in a manufacturing process. As a result we see that cooling towers are commonly used in 1. HVAC (Heating Ventilation and Air-Conditioning) to reject the heat from chillers 2. Manufacturing to provide process cooling 3. Electric power generation plants to provide cooling for the condenser Cooling tower operation is based on evaporative cooling as well as exchange of sensible heat. During evaporative cooling in a cooling tower, a small quantity of the water that is being cooled is evaporated in a moving stream of air to cool the rest of the water. Also when warm water comes in contact with cooler air, there is sensible heat transfer whereby the water is cooled. The major quantity heat transfer to the air is through evaporative cooling while only about 25% of the heat transfer is through sensible heat. Figure 1.1 taken from Mulyandasari [4] shows the schematic of a cooling tower.

Figure 1. Schematic of a Typical Mechanical Draft Cooling tower

Some important terms relating to cooling towers as described by Stanford [5] are:

- Approach- It is the difference between the temperature of water leaving the cooling tower and the wet bulb temperature. It is used as an indicator of how close to wet bulb temperature the water exiting the tower is.
- Free Cooling or Waterside Economizer Operation – It is the operation of the cooling tower in conditions where just the cooling tower is able to provide the required temperature cold water for HVAC or process needs without needing mechanical cooling from the chiller. This

saves energy because while the chiller may utilize about 0.7 kW/ton, the tower is now able to provide the same cooling at about 0.2 kW/ton. According to Hill [6] the factors influencing the performance of a cooling tower are:

1. The cooling range
2. The approach
3. The ambient wet bulb temperature
4. The flow rate of water through the tower
5. The flow rate of air over the water
6. The ambient temperature
7. The type of fill in the tower
8. Total surface area of contact between water and air

Figure 1.2 shows the graphical depiction of the tower classification

Figure 2 Classification of Cooling Towers

Classification by build

Package type cooling towers are preassembled and can be easily transported and erected at the location of use. These are generally suitable for applications where the heat load to be rejected is not very large (most HVAC and process load applications). Field erected type of towers are usually much larger to handle the larger heat rejection loads and are custom built as per customer requirements. Most of the Cooling Towers Classification based on Build Package type Field Erected

type Classification based on Heat Transfer Method Wet Cooling Tower Dry Cooling Tower Fluid Cooler Classification based on Type of Fill Spray Fill Splash Fill Film Fill Classification based on Air Draft Atmospheric Tower Natural Draft Tower Mechanical Draft Tower Forced Draft Induced Draft Classification based on Air Flow Pattern Crossflow Tower Counter Flow Tower construction /assembly of the tower takes place at the site where the tower will be located.

Figure 3 Cooling Tower Compact

In open evaporative cooling towers, the cooling of the water in the circuit occurs due to the evaporation of some of the water and the transfer of heat to the colder air flow. The heated water is fed through the water distribution system to the cooling tower and is sprayed through the nozzles. Further, the water flows down in a thin film down the cellular structure of the sprinkler channels. Along the channels of the sprinkler, in the opposite direction, the air flow moves. Since the air flow is large, the water partially evaporates, as a result of which, the rest of it is cooled. When 1% of water evaporates, the temperature of its remaining part is reduced by about 6 K. In this case, part of the water evaporates, part is carried away by the air flow. The proportion of evaporated water is in the range of 1.5-2%, therefore, its replenishment is required to replenish it. The chilled water flows into the sump, and

from there it is pumped into the condenser of the refrigerating machine (chiller) or into the cooled module of technological equipment.

The air flow in the cooling tower is forced and is created by an axial fan. The fan draws in air from several sides at the bottom of the tower and then blows it up. If the cooling tower is irrigation, then its direction can be counter-current or perpendicular to the direction of water flow. Only water can be used as a coolant in open-type cooling towers. Figure 3 shows a diagram of water cooling in a compact cooling tower.

This thesis will be to build a model that predicts the performance of package type towers. Although the performance of field erected type towers may be similar to package type towers, the predicted performance may not be very accurate as a result of the unique and requirement specific construction of field erected type towers. Classification based on heat transfer method Wet cooling towers are the most common type of cooling towers and the ones referred to when talking about cooling towers. As explained earlier, they operate on the principle of evaporative cooling. The water to be cooled and the ambient air come in direct contact with each other. This thesis will look mainly at the performance prediction of wet cooling towers since they are the most widely used. In a dry cooling tower there is a surface (e.g. tube of a heat exchanger) that separates the water from the ambient air. There is no evaporative cooling in this case. Such a tower may be used when the fluid to be cooled needs to be protected from the environment. In a fluid cooler water is sprayed over tubes through which the fluid to be cooled is flowing while a fan may also be utilized to provide a draft. This incorporates the mechanics of evaporative cooling in a wet cooling tower while also allowing the working fluid to be free of contaminants or environmental contact. Classification based on type of Fill In a spray fill tower the water is broken down into small droplets so that the area of contact between the water surface and air is increased. So in a way spray fill is

not really a fill because there is no packing in the tower. Small droplets of water are created by spraying through nozzles, which are contained within the tower casing, through which there is airflow. The drawbacks of this kind of a fill are low efficiency, large tower size and large airflow requirement.

Figure 4 laboratory view cooling tower

The drop catcher package has a thickness (in the direction of the air flow) not less than 75 mm, the width of the package is 140 mm. Sprinkler packages are stacked on a grid inside the cooling tower above the tank in one or two layers. The droplet separator packages are placed on a grid welded to the water distribution header between the collector pipes and the casing walls. The cooled water is supplied under pressure through the inlet pipe 7 to the water distribution manifold 6 and is sprayed with all-piece nozzles with a spray angle of 120° on the upper -3- end of the sprinkler package. Having passed through the channels of the sprinkler in the form of a film, water flows in jets into the tank. Air from the environment is supplied by the fan 2 directly into the space under the sprinkler, passes through the sprinkler channels towards the water film and leaves the cooling tower through the droplet catcher 5. Evaporative cooling of water occurs mainly in the channels of the sprinkler with counterflow of air and water film. Additional cooling takes place in the tank and in the space between the top edge of the sprinkler and the nozzles. In the hot season with a relative humidity of 50-60%, the minimum temperature of chilled water after the cooling tower is $3-4^\circ\text{C}$ higher than the temperature of the “wet” thermometer.

To prevent significant droplet entrainment of water, an effective droplet separator 5 is used. The water consumption for evaporation together with losses through the droplet separator (the smallest droplets) is about 1% of the water consumption. Water pressure in front of the nozzles according to the flow characteristic in Fig. 8 should be provided for by the design of the water supply system.

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